

OVERSEAS MIGRATION A BIG CHALLENGE IN NORTHERN REGION

Tripat Kaur

Assistant Professor in Sociology, Guru Arjan Dev Khalsa College, Chohla Sahib, Distt. Tarn Taran, Punjab

ABSTRACT

The present research paper is on overseas migration a very big challenge in northern region particularly in Punjab. The favourable social conditions and better social opportunities available in certain regions have drawn the flow of population faster to these regions. This research paper tried to explore those challenges which northern region is facing due to moving of large scale youth in overseas countries.

Keywords: Overseas, migration, favourable, challenges.

Migration is the result of the interplay between the expulsive forces at the place origin and attractive forces at the place of destination.

Migration : **Temporary movement.**

Immigration : **Permanent residency**

International migration if analysed then it will be found it is a worldwide phenomenon, and it has influenced every economy in the world.

Migration plays a significant role in the development of both home and host countries. But whenever it crosses its limits, then in place of development it becomes challenging.

From a sociological perspective, “Challenge” refers to a social issue or problem that affects a community or group of people within a society often stemming from structural inequalities or systematic issues and requiring complete solutions, that consider the broader social context, rather than just individual circumstances, challenges are not inherent but are socially constructed challenges. These are poverty, pollution, discrimination, crime and now it is the overseas migration.

In order to make a meaningful sociological analysis of migration in the present context, it needs to have a brief description of general trend of migration in world. The vast majority of people continue to live in the countries where they were born only one in thirty re migrants (World migration report – 2024).

The latest world migration report released by the International Organization for Migration confirms that migration from India to UAE, the US and Saudi Arabia ranks among the top 10 countries to country.

In 2020 approximately 18 million people from India were living outside their country of birth, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), the United States (US) and Saudi Arabia host the largest Indian diaspora both internal migration within the country, Migration to other countries are typically driven by the pursuit of improved livelihood.

In ‘The Hindu’ (2025) it was stated that as students’ emigrants from Kerala double in five years, seats in state universities remain vacant.

According to S. Irudaya Rajan, Chairman of International institute of Migration and Development. The trend of student migration will continue for the next 15 years due to demographic changes and rising aspirations. Student now constitute 11.3% of these members with younger individuals' a large number of seats in higher education institutes in the state remain unfulfilled.

A more recent survey conducted by professors at Punjab Agriculture University between 2021 and 2023 found that Panjabi's sold assets worth Rs. 5,636 crores including a portion of their land and borrowed a total amount of Rs. 14.342 crore to send their children abroad PAU;

Findings show in Chandigarh only an estimated 1.26 lac students went abroad for prosperous future between 2016 to 2021. Around one lakh students who leave Punjab every year rarely return.

The Times of India (2025) stated that 1,36,000 students from Punjab migrated to Canada in 2022. This becomes more significant when it is under consideration that Punjab only accounts for less than 2.5% of India's total population. This solid wave of immigration of Panjabi's has very serious impact on Punjab development.

Canada preferred destination for 42%. This report was indicated in PAU in Ludhiana. Youth of the state is migrating not only of "unemployment and agriculture distress; but also because of "rampant corruption" and unbridled prevalence of drugs.

Another factor responsible is India's tax regime is considered, severe rules about remittances.

Overseas passports offer greater mobility as per the Henley Passport Index 2023. Indian passport is ranked 80th.

POLLUTION FREE ENVIRONMENT.

Impacts

As mass immigration of students from Punjab can lead to brain drain in the future.

Secondly the economy of Punjab is based on agriculture. It adversely impacts on the economy of Punjab. As the visa process of developed countries is more complicated and also costs huge amount. Certain sociological approaches have pointed out during 2001. The migration process was very slow. The villagers have deep rooted and emotionally attached within their natives. This attachment exerts strong pressure on them to hold at their places of origin. more and more youth prodding their families to sell off lands to fund their fees, their travel expenses etc.

One of the most important institutions of the society is family. The normative order is a fundamentals concept in sociological thought. Norms are learn through the socialization in family. Human society could not exist without the normative order (Davis 1478'53). S socialization into the normative order begins within the family. Where the child learns to function within the framework of a given society (Elkin and Handel; 1972)

Previously or two decades ago family size and dependency ration is also facing challenge as youth parentally migrated to overseas regions leaving behind their aged parent alone. Approximately 13.34% of rural households in Punjab have at least one member living abroad.

As per the National Family Health Survey (2019-21), total fertility rate in Punjab was 1:6 lower than the replacement level of 2:1. This ratio was taken seriously that Sikhs were getting

reduced to a minority in the only Sikh majority state in the country due to prevailing trends of migration from other states into Punjab (the Times of India; 2025)

Marriage institute was the most sacramental institute previously, but now a days it has gone a drastic change in its structure. Contractual marriages her refer to arrangements between two families in which less educated person who cannot clear IELTS exam, sponsors a financially disadvantages yet bright girl student's studies abroad in exchange for a spouse visa. The contract remains between the two families. The marriage institution in Punjab is undergoing a significant shift. The trend of seeking NRI grooms has now been reversed and now there is search for IELTS holding girls.

A case study from India Today (2023) Gurpreet Singh, a resident of Moga filed a criminal case against his NRI wife, Gurpreet Kaur and her parents accusing them of cheating him of Rs. 25 lakhs.

In another case 23 year old Jatin Kumar died by suicide in January 2020 after his Canadian wife demanding more money for getting him settled abroad.

Amarjeet Singh from Hoshiarpur died by suicide in April 2023 after he was harassed by his NRI wife seeking money.

The above given case studies are very dew cases, that are given. In reality immigration have taken a very serious shape in Punjab, Govt. should take this issue primarily.

Here few humble suggestions are there to control overseas migration.

Govt. should focus on creating more job opportunities for youth.

To provide financial assistance or stipend to talented and skilled students who cannot afford higher education.

Corruption free system be created.

Govt. Should plan to increase the number of de-addiction and rehabilitation centres with recreational facilities for addicts.

Last but not least there is need for more comprehensive and effective measures to retain the youth and a create attractive environment within the state.

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